

Review Article

Metal nanoparticles based electrochemical biosensing of neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin biomarker for monitoring acute kidney injury

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ABSTRACT

Neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL), commonly known as Lipocalin-2 (LCN2), is a protein that is secreted by neutrophils and damaged renal tubular epithelial cells. This 25-kDa secretory protein with 178 amino acids can be detected in both urine and plasma samples. NGAL serves as a marker for kidney injury, and its release is triggered exclusively when the kidneys experience stress due to inflammation and infection. Urinary NGAL is generated within the renal tubules, exactly in the thick ascending limb of Henle and the collecting-ducts. The conventional analytical approaches for the detection of NGAL urinary markers display some key limitations, including being expensive, time-consuming, often inaccurate, and practically difficult to apply for the analysis. Interestingly, the development of nanomaterials in biology and medicine has provided an ideal solution to the early diagnosis and treatment of acute kidney injury (AKI). Thus, in this review, we emphasize the development of electrochemical biosensors for NGAL detection, which covers the principle, key design, and biosensor strategies using functionalized nanomaterial-based (carbon nanostructures, metal nanoclusters, metal nanoparticles, metal-organic frameworks, and quantum dots) electroanalytical detection methods. The analytical outcomes of these electrochemical biosensors are also compared and summarized with relevant clinical samples. This promising discipline, at the interface of nanomaterials and biosciences, provides wide prospects for interdisciplinary researchers that comprise nanomaterial preparation, biological functionalization, biosensor platforms, and targeted theranostics in biomedical diagnostics. The potential strategies for new electrode design, important biosensing characteristics, key challenges, and future opportunities toward NGAL determination are also described.

1. Introduction

Kidney biomarkers are molecules, often proteins or enzymes, that can be measured in biological samples such as blood, urine, saliva, sweat, or tissue to assess the function and health of the kidneys. These biomarkers play a crucial role in diagnosing kidney diseases, monitoring kidney function, and predicting the outcomes of kidney-related conditions [1]. Kidney disease diagnosis has traditionally depended on serum creatinine, a cost-effective and widely available marker, despite its long-standing limitations, such as delayed detection of kidney damage [2]. In

the context of AKI, novel biomarkers like NGAL, kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM-1), and cystatin C have emerged as valuable indicators that can provide early and specific information about renal damage [3]. Biomarkers such as NGAL and interleukin-18 (IL-18) have shown great promise in the early detection of AKI after cardiac surgery and liver transplantation, aiding in timely interventions and improved patient outcomes [4].

NGAL, alternatively referred to as LCN2, is a protein molecule that is produced by neutrophils and is present in various human tissues, such as kidney tubular cells, lungs, heart, colon, liver, stomach, dendritic cells,

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Fig. 1. Expression of NGAL urinary biomarkers in various human tissues. .
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etc. (Fig. 1). This 25-kDa secretory protein with 178 amino acids can be detected in both urine and plasma samples [5–7]. Over recent years, NGAL has garnered attention as a promising marker for diagnosing AKI, largely due to its exceptional specificity and dependability [8]. NGAL serves as a marker for kidney injury, and its release is triggered exclusively when the kidneys experience stress due to inflammation and infection. Urinary NGAL is generated within the renal tubules, particularly in the thick ascending limb of Henle and the collecting-ducts [9]. Recent research has shown a connection between initial tubular abnormalities in non-albuminuric individuals with type 1 diabetes and NGAL [10]. Consequently, utilizing NGAL levels for diagnosis can aid in the early recognition of individuals at a higher risk of diabetes-associated AKI. This approach can facilitate the early detection of AKI and, in turn, help prevent diabetic nephropathy [8]. Notably, NGAL levels are typically low in healthy individuals and rise during infectious diseases and renal tubular injury. They increase significantly within the initial hours after renal injury, when potential reversibility exists. This makes it an ideal candidate for early detection of kidney damage, assessing its severity, enhancing chronic kidney disease (CKD) diagnosis and prognosis, and evaluating treatment effectiveness [6]. The typical urinary NGAL level for healthy individuals falls within the range of 9–49.41 ng/mL, with variations based on age and physical health. However, in cases of AKI, renal tubular cells can release substantial amounts of NGAL (97 ng/mL), elevating NGAL levels to over 133 ng/mL, potentially indicating the development of CKD [11,12].

2. Conventional methods-based detection of NGAL

Various methods and approaches have been devised to quantitatively or qualitatively detect NGAL, utilizing diverse signal-generation principles. Some of the methods encompass up-converting phosphor lateral flow tests, ion chromatography, cross flow filtration, and solid-phase proximity ligation-assays [14–16]. Commercially accessible urine tests for rapid NGAL measurement rely on immunoassay techniques, including chemiluminescent microparticle immunoassay (CMIA) [17], particle-enhanced turbidimetric immunobioassay (PETIA) [18], and sandwich-type enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) [19–23]. For instance, Krzeminska et al., reported the detection of NGAL in urine samples up to a level of 3.5 ng/mL and 4.4 ng/mL using the CLMI and ELISA methods, respectively [20]. Wagener et al., developed an immunoblotting method for the detection of NGAL in real urine samples and established a valuable assay for monitoring acute renal dysfunction and subsequently acute renal failure in patients' post-cardiac surgical treatment [22]. Singer et al., used the CLMI (Abbott Architect) method for the determination of NGAL for potential clinical applications, though they determined the concentrations of NGAL during the diagnosis of AKI treatment, which is almost end-stage renal illness in the longer term or even close to the patient's death [23].

Subsequently, Salvagno et al., developed a protocol for the quantification of NGAL in actual serum samples employing PETIA. The collected patient's real serum samples were mixed with immune particles comprised of anti-NGAL, which then formed an immunocomplex and enhanced the turbidity of the mixture. As a result, the concentrations of NGAL were measured by the absorbance changes. Using the PETIA method, a wide linear range of NGAL was achieved from 37 to 1420 ng/mL, and the limit of detection (LOD) was found to be 6.30 ng/mL [24]. In the meantime, Gombert et al. introduced the ELISA method to determine the NGAL levels in patients' actual urine samples who suffered from thoracoabdominal aortic aneurysm (TAA) disease. The developed ELISA approach was used to detect NGAL at post-operation, which is highly beneficial for the prognosticator of AKI [25]. On the other side, Jacobsen et al., introduced a commercially accessible porcine-specific ELISA (ps-ELISA) assay to detect equine NGAL from blood serum samples. It was demonstrated that the ps-ELISA can detect the projected variances of NGAL levels in equine with usual and abnormal concentrations from the serum samples [26]. Among the conventional methods, CMIA and PETIA offer quick results and high sensitivity, but they rely on specialized personnel and sophisticated instruments. Despite the good performance of ELISA, some key drawbacks, such as costly reagents, complex sample preparation, and extended testing times, indirectly hinder clinical diagnostic advancements. Hence, it's imperative to devise a convenient, swift, and effective approach for NGAL detection [27].

3. Strategies for the implementation of nanomaterials for enhancing sensor performance

The construction of sensing systems is mainly comprised of nanomaterials, such as metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, graphene, graphene oxides (GOx), graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄), and polymer composites, since they can enhance the analytical performance due to their excellent electronic conductivity, larger active surface area, catalytic active sites, porous nature, longer stability, and biocompatibility [28–32]. For instance, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are one of the most commonly used nanomaterials for the design and fabrication of numerous electrochemical biosensing interfaces. Further, AuNPs can be conveniently multi-functionalized with various organic or biomolecule ligands, including antibodies, aptamers, peptides, graphene, polymer nanocomposites, etc., which can enhance the attributes of sensing performances [33–35].

On the other side, graphene, GOx, g-C₃N₄, and polymer composites have carbon-atoms on all their surfaces, which enabling facile interaction with various biomolecules [36,37]. For instance, the covalent modification of graphene has considerably enhanced the utility of these materials for various sensor applications. This covalent modification is generally achieved via two-routes: (i) the activation of the graphene by

Fig. 2. A pictorial representation displaying the stepwise assembly of the NGAL biosensor electrode using CA/MUA, GA, NGAL protein/NGAL peptide, and NGAL protein. .

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creating reactive species such as $-OH$, $-NH_2$, and $-COOH$ groups; and (ii) the direct covalent functionalization of the suitable functional groups using various reactions (cycloaddition, electrophilic, and nucleophilic addition). The efficient non-covalent modification of graphene is achieved using $CH-\pi$ interactions, $\pi-\pi$ interactions, electrostatic interactions, and van der Waals attraction, which indeed offer potential sensing platforms with desirable characteristics for the detection of various biomolecules [38–41]. Polymers are often combined with noble and/or non-noble nanoparticles (Cu, Co, Au, Ag, etc.) to produce nanocomposites with excellent inherent properties (opto-electronic and catalytic), which enhance their catalytic efficiency within the 0-D to 3-D matrix and also their sensing performances [42–44]. On the other side, the combination of MXene/polyaniline and MOF has increased chemical reactivity due to its large warps, good electrocatalytic efficacy, and large active surface area; carbon fiber was also used as the transducing surface for electrochemical sensing system owing to its physico-chemical and biocompatible properties [45,46].

The difference in device-to-device properties (e.g., conductance, *trans*-conductance, and source/drain current) and analytical performances of nanomaterials-based sensing platforms (e.g., sensitivity, selectivity, LOD, and LOQ) constitutes a key factor in the various practical applications of such designed sensors. Remarkably, the nanomaterial-based construction of sensing approaches is effectively enabling affiliated and synergistic implementation to further boost the sensitivity and selectivity performance of designed sensors. Several approaches have been developed to resolve this analytical blockade and enhance the NGAL sensor outcome, including AuNPs, galinstan nanoparticles (GaNPs), and carbon-based nanomaterials (e.g., $g-C_3N_4$, 3-D graphene, and self-assembled layers) [8,9,12,47–51]. Such approaches diminish the variability of analytical performance and significantly enhance the properties of sensing systems, mainly because of the exclusivity of combined nanostructures and bioelements. Thus, the unique catalytic activities of these nanomaterials permit researchers to construct novel and advanced electrochemical sensing approaches with enhanced sensitivity, selectivity, and stability of NGAL, which were discussed as follows:

4. Electrochemical methods-based detection of NGAL

Electrochemical immunosensors have garnered significant interest due to their ability to facilitate specific antigen–antibody reactions [52–54]. An efficient immunosensor employs antibodies, antibody fragments, antigens, or redox proteins to track the binding interactions within bio-electrochemical reactions [53,55–60]. To achieve highly efficient electrochemical immunoassays with a low LOD and limit of

quantification (LOQ), a key consideration is the utilization of advanced signal-generation tags [54,61–63]. Commonly, standard procedures utilize ligand-conjugated enzyme markers or nanoscale labels. Traditional enzymes like horseradish peroxidase and alkaline phosphatase are frequently used to generate signals. Unfortunately, their catalytic efficiency often requires electron mediators like ferricyanide, thionine, or ferrocene derivatives during electrochemical measurements, which can lead to system contamination and interference [64]. Enzyme-substrate reactions are sensitive to factors like incubation conditions and inhibitory agents [65]. Therefore, an alternative immunosensing approach based on electrochemical principles that eliminates the need for enzyme labeling would offer distinct advantages.

Unlike the standard analytical methods, electrochemical immunosensors combined with nanomaterials are recognized as a smart choice for creating sensitive, rapid, and, notably, straightforward and easily accessible detection methods, serving as a replacement technique for the available current approaches [54,61,66]. Nanomaterials are tiny building blocks; they can be synthesized from both organic and inorganic materials and display many exclusive features, for example, a higher surface-to-volume ratio, higher active sites, and enhanced detection sensitivity in various studies including energy, catalysis, and sensors [67–72]. Functional nanomaterials offer significant benefits such as simple fabrication procedures, higher sensitivity, higher accuracy, enhanced stability, absorbability, low cost, and biocompatibility [72–75]. For instance, the growth of nanoscale functional materials is playing a vital role in modern nanotechnology and medicine, which eases the trace-level detection of various biomarkers in real samples [76–80]. The key benefit of these nanomaterials involves the fabrication of advanced biosensing substrates for improved electron transport in electrochemical reactions via bioactive sites for the detection of AKI biomarkers, including NGAL [48,81,82]. Therefore, the evaluation of initial and specific biomarkers is of critical and clinical importance for monitoring the beginning and development of renal disorders. In this regard, active treatment could be directed to avert the AKI and decrease difficulties such as contagion, anemia, hypertension, and cardiac failure. Thus, bio-elements such as peptides, aptamers, and antibodies coupled with a nanostructured detection platform may be vital for the initial recognition of NGAL with substantial sensitivity, which is certainly more advantageous than currently available traditional analytical methods.

4.1. Peptides-based detection of NGAL

The prevailing assays for NGAL level detection predominantly utilize antibodies as biorecognition components, and they entail multi-step sample preparation, occasionally necessitating suitable labeling

Fig. 3. Patterning process of MIP film with the convex-hemispherical pore arrays obtained by NGAL protein surface imprinting and photo-polymerization step, followed by the MIP surface bonded with NGAL-BP1 protein (a). The high and low magnified SEM views of the fabricated MIP films interacted with NGAL BP1 (b, c) and the corresponding NGAL extracted MIP (d, e).

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procedures [83]. The synthesis of antibodies tends to be costly, and their binding capabilities are susceptible to deterioration in unfavorable conditions, with potential issues related to cross-reactivity [84,85]. To overcome these constraints, several efficient affinity reagents, such as aptamers [86], peptide nucleic acids [87], peptides [88], and alternative assay materials [89], have been devised. Among these options, peptides stand out as an attractive choice due to their cost-effective synthesis and superior stability when compared to antibodies [90,91], which suggests their suitability for usage in NGAL biosensors. The phage display method is a potent approach for discovering distinctive, unique peptide motifs that exhibit binding affinity to various targets, ranging from non-organic substances to biomarkers associated with diseases [85,91]. Peptides obtained through the M13 phage show library/or phages presenting peptides have been employed as antibody substitutes in the creation of bio-imaging probes. These probes serve as innovative scaffolding materials with a broad spectrum of potential uses [92]. Cho et al., demonstrated an electrochemical biosensor that integrated an affinity peptide for NAGL detection in patients' plasma samples [8]. The utilization of biopanning from the M13 phage displayed a library against the immobilized NGAL, which resulted in the rapid determination of a distinctive affinity peptide with the amino acid arrangement of DRWVARDPASIF. These peptide sequences exhibited specific binding to phage particles towards NGAL detection. In order to facilitate the progress of an electrochemical biosensor-based on peptides, a set of synthetically designed phage particle-derived peptides designed with a systematic approach were chemically synthesized and affixed to the surface of the gold sensor layer, such as cysteamine (CA), mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA), amino acids, and NGAL peptides/phages (Fig. 2). Out of the five-synthetic peptide compounds evaluated, NGAL BP1

emerged as the most favorable recognition receptor because of its higher binding affinity assessed through SWV and EIS methods (Fig. 2). The EIS technique exhibited an LOD of 1.74 ng/mL, and the SWV technique exhibited a LOD of 3.93 ng/mL [8]. The sensing capacity of the peptide-integrated sensor closely matched that of commercial ELISA-based NGAL detection tools. Furthermore, the peptide sensor was validated by testing it with plasma samples obtained from patients, demonstrating a statistically significant difference in sensitivity. These findings suggest the combined phage and peptide sensors offer the potential for highly sensitive and selective NGAL detection, making them a viable biosensing assay for tracking NGAL within a compact electrochemical biosensor [8].

Molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs), sometimes called synthetic antibodies, have found utility as substitute ligands for molecular and biomolecular recognition in diverse fields, such as bioanalytical systems and active targeting tools in the field of medicine [93,94]. These effective antibody-mimicking agents, distinguished by their strong affinity and specificity for their respective targets, are created through a standard polymerization process involving functional monomers that mimic the dimension, configuration, and electrical charge distribution of the template molecule [95]. MIPs offer significant benefits, including being reproducible, affordable, and chemically stable, making them a prevalent choice for the detection of diverse molecules [96,97]. Nevertheless, the imprinting of substantial biomolecules like cells or proteins presents several challenges [98]. Firstly, MIPs are typically synthesized in aggressive organic solvents, which can lead to the denaturation of biomolecules. Secondly, the potential for template leakage can reduce detection precision. Residual template molecules persisting within MIPs, despite rigorous washing, can influence the outcomes of qualitative or

Fig. 4. Modification steps of Au/MXene/PANI and Pep/Au/Cu-MOF/SWNHs (A, B) and graphic display of the NGAL biosensor electrode using the components derived from A, B. .

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quantitative tests [99]. Lastly, MIPs exhibit a multitude of nonspecific binding sites due to the inherently 'polyclonal' nature of their binding profiles [98]. In response to the difficulties mentioned, researchers have explored various alternatives, such as epitope immobilization [100], solid-phase synthesis [101], nanoparticle fabrication [102], and the use of water-soluble polymers [103]. Surface imprinting techniques are widely employed to detect biomolecules at high-affinity binding sites. Lately, several techniques have been implemented for surface imprinting to overcome the limitations associated with bulk imprinting [104–106]. Nonetheless, as imprinted cavities form solely on the surface of the polymer matrix, the quantity of recognition sites available for the detection of analytes is limited. This limitation leads to reduced sensing capacity and signal amplification. Consequently, utilizing lithography techniques to structure the surface of MIPs represents a capable strategy for expanding the imprinted surface area by employing micro- and nano-scale patterning. The structured MIPs were generated through electrochemical polymerization, employing a micro/nano-patterned framework that was adapted with proteins acting as a temporary sacrificial mask. This approach facilitated the convenient detection of protein analytes. Considered as salient key points, Yang et al., reported molecular-affinity-peptide-imprinted polymer films as an alternative sensing platform for the detection of NGAL. A film with molecularly imprinted peptides, specifically binding to BP1, was created using a cross-linked poly(acrylamide-co-diallylamine-co-N, N'-methylenebisacrylamide) matrix through photochemical techniques. This film was deposited on a gold-coated quartz crystal electrode to enable the detection of NGAL (Fig. 3a) [51]. Microcontact surface imprinting involved the utilization of a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) mold featuring a concave hemispherical array containing the BP1 template to create patterned films. The surface characteristics of these fabricated MIP films interacted with NGAL BP1 was denoted as imprinted MIP (I-MIP), and NGAL-extracted MIP was labeled as E-MIP, as shown in (Fig. 3b–e) [51].

The LOD of the biosensor was determined to be 0.07 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and the LOQ was about 0.24 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Additionally, the performance of (NGAL-BP1)-imprinted MIP, referred to as "I-MIP," in assisting biosensors for

the detection of NGAL was studied by DPV and EIS methods. The normalized current peak (I_N) and impedance (R_N) values exhibited a linear increase within the NGAL concentration range of 1 to 300 ng/mL. Notably, the selectivity coefficient (k^*) of NGAL proteins on the BP1-imprinted film was found to be 3.5–5.8 compared to bovine serum albumin, indicating a strong interaction between the imprinted BP1 peptide and the NGAL protein. Significant impedance differences were observed at various phases of inflammatory bowel disease when using biosensors for adsorbing NGAL proteins in real patient samples. Furthermore, the NGAL levels determined with the I-MIP-assisted biosensors developed were in good agreement with commercially available ELISA kits. Thus, EIS-based biosensors utilizing peptide-imprinted matrices hold great potential for the detection of macromolecular proteins in clinical applications.

Metal organic frameworks (MOFs) have gained immense interest due to their versatility in numerous applications, such as electrocatalysis, gas storage, proton transport, and biomedical imaging, making them a noteworthy class of hybrid materials with both organic and inorganic components [107,108]. They exhibit numerous benefits in the area of electrochemical biosensors because of their versatility, adaptable structures, exceptional porosity, and expansive specific surface area [109]. Using the goodness of MOFs, Liang et al., designed a dual-signal electrochemical biosensor for NGAL detection, utilizing a combination of MXene-polyaniline and copper-MOF/single-walled carbon nanohorn structures (Cu-MOF/SWNHs) [48]. The synthesis of nanocomposites, consisting of MXene-loaded polyaniline (MXene/PANI), was carried out, and these nanocomposites served as the fundamental sensing framework for attaching AuNPs and fixing primary antibodies (Fig. 4A). Following that, a nanocomposite consisting of AuNPs-loaded Cu-MOF/SWNHs (Au/Cu-MOF/SWNHs) was synthesized by depositing AuNPs onto Cu-MOF/SWNHs. Then NGAL affinity peptide (Pep) was attached to Au/Cu-MOF/SWNHs, forming a Pep/Au/Cu-MOF/SWNHs nanocomposite, which functioned as a probe (Fig. 4B). A sensitive sandwich-type immunosensor was developed using SWV and amperometric (i-t) techniques. The above developed probe exhibited a significant SWV signal (referred to as signal 1), which resulted from the transfer of electrons

Fig. 5. Stepwise fabrication of NGAL biosensor electrode using ATT-GO, AuNPs, Apt-1, MCH, LCN2, biotinylated Apt-2, streptavidin-ALP. . Reproduced with permission from Ref. [47]

from Cu^{2+} to Cu^+ within Cu-MOF. The *i-t* signal (signal 2) was acquired as a result of H_2O_2 reduction by the Au/Cu-MOF/SWNHs demonstrating their superior electrocatalytic performance. (Fig. 4C) [48]. The Au/Cu-MOF/SWNHs exhibited outstanding performance in analytical applications over a linear range spanning from 0.00001 to 10.00 ng/mL. The LOD for NGAL determination was measured at 0.0074 pg/mL (SWV) and 0.0405 pg/mL (*i-t*). This immunosensor was further applied for NGAL detection in samples, showcasing its potential for use in the diagnosis of AKI [48].

4.2. Aptamers-based detection of NGAL

Aptamers, short sequences of synthetic DNA or RNA oligonucleotides or peptides, are capable of specifically recognizing diverse targets, including proteins [110], cells [111], small molecules [112,113], and microorganisms [114]. Their widespread adoption can be attributed to

their potential for reuse, stability, and adaptability for modifying functional groups [115]. Consequently, biosensors based on aptamers have garnered extensive attention for applications in the analysis of pesticides, genetic screening, and clinical assessments in the last few years [116–118]. Moreover, new-generation aptasensors can be designed to detect a wide array of molecules by employing different electrochemical methods like CV, LSV CA, and EIS. For instance, Gozde et al., engineered an aptasensor based on the electrochemical sandwich format to detect NGAL, employing graphene oxide polymer composites and AuNP. The aptasensor was developed using a composite of poly-3-amino-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol/graphene oxide (P-(ATT)-GO) and AuNPs on a modified graphite-SPE denoted as GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/AuNPs (Fig. 5) [47], which is the key platform for the further progress of a sandwich-assay used for the NGAL quantification.

Firstly, a DNA aptamer with a thiol group was immobilized onto the AuNPs-ATT-GO composite electrode. Secondly, a solution containing

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of label-free aptamer-based detection of NGAL via cascade-recycling enhancement approach. . Reproduced with permission from Ref. [82]

Table 1
Peptide and aptamers functionalized nanostructured biosensing detection of NGAL in various real samples.

Biosensing Platform	Biosensor Construction Steps	Linear Limit	Detection Method	LOD	Real Samples	Ref.
Affinity peptide-incorporated electrochemical biosensor	<p>Steps involved: 4</p> <p>Route I: (i) the modification of cysteamine (CA) on the surface of the Au electrode; (ii) the introduction of glutaldehyde (GA) on the surface of CA/Au through EDC-NHS coupling chemistry (GA/CA/Au); (iii) the GA/CA/Au electrode was incubated with NGAL protein; and (iv) the NGAL precoated electrode was interacted with peptide-showed phage particles, and the binding affinity was analyzed by CV, EIS, and SWV.</p> <p>Route II: (i) the modification of MUA on the surface of the Au electrode; (ii) the introduction of EDC-NHS coupling agents on the surface of the MUA/Au electrode; (iii) the synthetic NGAL peptide was introduced on the surface of the MUA/Au electrode (NGAL peptide/MUA/Au); and (iv) NGAL proteins were further immobilized on the surface of the NGAL peptide/MUA/Au (NGAL protein/NGAL peptide/MUA/Au), then the binding affinity was analyzed by CV, EIS, and SWV.</p>	0.0001 µg/mL to 7.50 µg/mL	EIS and SWV	1.74 ng/mL (by EIS; 3 σ/S) 3.93 ng/mL (by SWV; 3 σ/S)	Crude blood or plasma	[8]
Metal ion-dependent DNzyme- and Exo III-triggered recycling signal enhancement cascades	<p>Steps involved: 5</p> <p>(i) The Au electrode surface was initially modified by hairpin H1; (ii) The H1/Au electrode was incubated with MCH (MCH/H1/Au) as a blocking agent, which covers non-specific sites; (iii) the DNA-duplex probe is generated through a hybridizing of Apt with S1 (Apt/S1). The metal ion-dependent S1 cannot be released from Apt/S1, and the Exo III cleavage reaction is repressed owing to the fact that Apt/S1 is an inactive substrate for Exo III in the absence of NGAL; (iv) the NGAL binding with Apt in the Apt/S1 duplex enables the release of the DNzyme sequence of S1, which relates to and cleaves the substrate H1 on the sensor electrode with aid of Mg²⁺ to recycle S1 and to release a strand that can complement the Apt sequence; and (v) with help of K⁺, the free-strands fold- and bind with hemin to generate G-quadruplex/hemin complex, which limit several hemin in the vicinity of the NGAL sensor surface.</p>	25–150 ng/mL	DPV	4.45 ng/mL (3 σ/s)	Diluted human serums	[82]
AuNP-loaded Cu-MOF decorated with SWNHs nanocomposite	<p>Steps involved: 5</p> <p>(i) The GCE surface was modified with Au/MXene/PANI, (ii) Au/MXene/PANI/GCE immobilized into primary capture antibody (Ab1/Au/MXene/PANI/GCE), (iii) the introduction of BSA on the surface of Ab1/Au/MXene/PANI/GCE (BSA/Ab1/Au/MXene/PANI/GCE), (iv) the introduction of NGAL into BSA/Ab1/Au/MXene/PANI/GCE (NGAL/BSA/Ab1/Au/MXene/PANI/GCE), and finally (v) the signal probe was used to detect the NGAL by SWV and CA methods.</p>	0.00001 – 10 ng/mL	SWV and i-t	0.0074 pg/mL (SWV; 3 α/b) 0.0405 pg/mL (i – t; 3 α/b)	Artificial serum and real serum	[48]
Specific binding peptide (BP1)-imprinted film comprised with cross-linked poly-(acrylamide-co-diallylamine-co-N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide) matrix	<p>Steps involved: 5</p> <p>(i) Fabrication of polystyrene colloidal monolayer (PDMS-mold), (ii) generation of hexagonally spotted pores on the PDMS-mold, (iii) Fabrication of oxidized PDMS-mold, (iv) photochemical treatment of poly-(acrylamide-co-diallylamine-co-N, N'-methylenebisacrylamide) matrix on the oxidized PDMS-mold, and finally (v) binding peptide (BP1)-imprinted PDMS-mold was used for the detection of NGAL.</p>	1 to 300 ng/mL	EIS	0.07 µg/mL (Signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3)	Blood serum	[51]
P-(ATT)-GO composite and AuNPs modified GSPE (GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/AuNPs).	<p>Steps involved:</p> <p>(i) electrodeposition of P-(ATT)-GO and followed by the immobilization of AuNPs on the GSPE; (ii) GSPEs were soaked into –SH-DNA aptamer (Apt1); (iii) the GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/Apt1 was then immersed into MCH as a blocking agent for protecting non-specific interactions; (iv) the GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/Apt1 was submerged with various concentrations of LCN2; (v) the obtained GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/Apt1/LCN2 electrode was integrated with biotinylated Apt2, and finally, the GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/Apt1/LCN2/Apt2 electrode was submerged into streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase solution and BSA for the detection of NGAL.</p>	1–1000 ng/mL	DPV	0.30 ng/mL (3 s/m)	Fetal bovine serum	[47]

* “s/m”, “σ/s”, and “3 α/b” are represented same analysis condition.

Fig. 7. Fabrication of the immunosensing substrate using boronic acid functionalized magnetic graphene nanoribbons for the detection of lymphoma cancer cells. . Reproduced with permission from Ref. [134]

LCN2 (NAGL) was submerged with the aptamer-modified GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/AuNPs. Thirdly, a secondary aptamer (Apt-2) specific to NAGL, labeled with biotin, was then introduced to interact with NAGL. Further enhancement was achieved by modifying a streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase conjugate on the electrode's surface (Fig. 5). The detection of NAGL relied on the electroactive characteristics of α -naphthol, a product formed through the reaction of alkaline phosphatase with α -naphthyl phosphate [47]. The aptamer-modified GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/AuNPs exhibited excellent electrocatalytic efficiency for NAGL detection by voltammetry, displaying a broad linear range from 1.0 to 1000.0 ng/mL and an LOD of 0.30 ng/mL. This aptasensor demonstrated outstanding reproducibility, sensitivity, and interference resistance, highlighting the potential of GSPE/P-(ATT)-GO/AuNPs as a potential candidate for the precise detection of NAGL. In addition, the developed aptabiosensor was employed to detect NAGL in fetal bovine serum samples through the conventional addition method, which delivered recovery values ranging from 99.20 to 103.22 % [47].

Enhancing the sensitivity of biomolecule detection in electrochemical sensing assays can be achieved through the incorporation of diverse amplification techniques, including strand displacement reactions [119], hybridization chain reactions [120], utilization of nanomaterials [121], rolling circle amplification [122], DNAzymes [123], and nuclease-assisted amplification strategies [124]. Among these methods, nuclease-assisted and DNAzyme amplification stand out as effective and potent signal enhancement techniques, thanks to their straightforward procedures and impressive amplification capabilities [125]. One notable enzyme is Exo III, which has the ability to progressively degrade and eliminate single nucleotides from the 3' recessive or blunt end of double-stranded DNA (dsDNA). However, it exhibits limited catalytic activity when confronted with 3' protruding dsDNA or single-

stranded DNA [126,127]. Given Exo III's robust catalytic capabilities and its lack of requirement for definite substrate sequences, signal enhancement techniques involving Exo III have gained traction for the development of universal biosensing platforms [127,128]. Yang et al., introduced a label-free aptamer-based electrochemical biosensor for highly sensitive detection of NGAL utilizing a cascading signal amplification approach that combined metal ion-dependent DNAzyme-based cyclic sequence cleavage with Exo III-mediated sequence recycling (Fig. 6) [82].

NGAL molecules were attached to the aptamer strands within the DNAzyme/aptamer duplex, leading to the release of metal-ion-dependent DNAzyme sequences (Fig. 6A). These released sequences then cut the hairpin signal probes located at the electrode site, resulting in the liberation of G-quadruplex and transitional strands (Fig. 6B). Subsequently, these liberated transitional strands form a suitable substrate for Exo III by interacting with the DNAzyme/aptamer duplex. Exo III digests duplex, releasing DNAzyme strands and initiating a cascading recycling process that yields a significant quantity of G-quadruplex strands. Hemin molecules interact with these G-quadruplex strands, forming numerous G-quadruplex/hemin complexes. The electrochemically reduced hemin produces a greatly amplified current (Fig. 6C), enabling NGAL detection with an LOD of 4.45 ng/mL. This biosensor exhibits a strong degree of selectivity and is suitable for tracking NGAL levels in diluted human serum samples with a recovery range of 95.60–104.20 %, indicating its potential for extension to the detection of various protein biomarkers associated with different aptamers, which could be valuable for disease diagnosis [82]. The summary peptide and aptamer-based functionalized nanostructured detection of NGAL in various real samples is described in Table 1.

Fig. 8. Fabrication of electrochemical NGAL immunoassay using monoclonal anti-NGAL antibody (mAb1)-modified SPCE and polyclonal anti-NGAL antibody (pAb2)-modified PB-NP-decorated $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ (pAb2/PB- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) nanocomposites. . Reproduced with permission from Ref. [9]

4.3. Antibody-based detection of NGAL

Antibodies are generally used as a gold-standard bio-recognition component for the electrochemical detection of NGAL due to their exclusive antibody-antigen chemistry. Notably, antibodies comprise an explicit binding site known as an epitope, which engages in a specific interaction with target entities. It is also important in an electrochemical biosensor; downsizing the working electrode is a common practice to enhance portability of the biosensor's platform and compatibility (use of biological samples with low-volume), such as urine, blood serum, saliva, sweat, etc., However, reducing the size of the working electrode unavoidably leads to a limitation in surface area, subsequently affecting the sensitivity of the biosensor adversely. Consequently, additional modifications to the working electrode become necessary in order to enhance the electrochemical sensitivity of the biosensor. Over the past few years, there has been a growing utilization of carbon-based nanomaterials, including carbon nanotubes [129], carbon nanofibers [130], carbon nanodots [131], and graphene [132], to improve the efficiency of working electrodes in terms of electrochemical capabilities. Graphene, comprising a lone layer of carbon atoms organized in a hexagonal honeycomb lattice, possesses remarkable physical and chemical properties [133–135]. For instance, Bagheri and co-workers developed a potential approach for the well-oriented functionalization of antibodies on the surface of boronic acid (BA)-tethered magnetic graphene nanoribbons (MGNRs) as an immunosensing substrate for the ultrasensitive detection of lymphoma cancer cells (Fig. 7) [134]. Notably, iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) nanoparticles incorporated MGNs (MGNRs; Step I) and served as the anchoring substrate for the functionalization of BA via the reaction between the $-\text{COOH}$ groups of MGNRs and the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups of BA through EDC-NHS chemistry, and the obtained substrate was denoted as BA-MGNRs (Step II). BA from BA-MGNRs was dynamically created as a supporting matrix, which enabled an ideal environment for immobilizing anti-CD20 antibodies (Anti-CD20 Abs) through electrostatic interaction between BA and the carbohydrate functional chains in the Fc domain of the Anti-CD20 Abs molecules (Anti-CD20 Abs/BA-MGNRs; Step III). Subsequently, BSA was introduced to block the remaining active sites and prevent non-specific binding (BSA/Anti-CD20 Abs/BA-MGNRs; Step IV) [134]. Finally, the as-fabricated BSA/Anti-CD20 Abs/BA-MGNRs were premixed into whole-blood real samples to specifically interact with lymphoma cancer cell receptors (Step V). In particular, the effective formation of an immunocomplex occurred

between anti-CD20 Abs and lymphoma cancer cell receptors; as a result, the immunocomplex was magnetically collected using a screen-printed electrode and subsequently tested by impedimetric measurements. The fabricated BSA/Anti-CD20 Abs/BA-MGNRs exhibited wide linear detection of lymphoma cancer cells ranging from 100 to 1,000,000 cells and achieved an ultralow detection limit of 38 cells/mL. Further, the developed immunosensor assay was highly specific against several potential interferents, such as human embryonic kidney (HEK293), breast cancer (MCF-7), and leukaemia (HL-60 and KCL-22) cell lines. The practical performance of the developed immunosensor was that it potentially detected lymphoma cancer cells in clinical whole-blood real samples, which was reliable with commercial flow-cytometric assays [134].

To prevent graphene clustering, conducting polymers are employed in combination with graphene for the modification of electrode surfaces [136]. The creation of a nanocomposite comprising both graphene and conducting polymers makes this hybrid nanomaterial better suited for fabricating electrodes and the introduction of biofunctional elements compared to using pure graphene alone. It has been documented that the utilization of electrodes modified with graphene/or conducting polymer nanocomposites markedly improves the electrochemical sensitivity of sensors [137,138]. Among the different conducting polymers used (polyaniline (PANI), polypyrrole, and poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)), PANI stands out as particularly attractive due to its affordability, simple synthesis, strong stability in various environmental conditions, reversible redox properties, and excellent compatibility with bio-compounds [139]. For instance, Yukird et al., developed a label-free immunosensor utilizing graphene/PANI nanocomposite for NAGL detection [50]. The immunoassay was developed by immobilizing NGAL capture antibodies onto an electro-polymerized aniline layer deposited onto a screen-printed carbon electrode modified with electro-sprayed graphene/polyaniline (G/PANI). Notably, electro-spraying G/PANI composite effectively increased the surface area of the electrode, and electropolymerization of aniline augmented the availability of amino groups ($-\text{NH}_2$) for the immobilization of antibodies. Various aspects influencing biosensor sensitivity, including scan rate, concentration of aniline, and electropolymerization scan number, were meticulously optimized. In this investigation, a remarkable 58-fold enhancement in oxidation current was observed when NGAL was bound to its antibody in comparison to an unaltered electrode [50]. This significant increase validates a substantial enhancement in the

Fig. 9. (A) An interfacial dipole layer between the GF and Ni interface. (B) NGAL bindings with anti-NCN2 through electron transfer concurrently among enormous active sites/mass of GF/AuNPs/anti-NCN2. . Reproduced with permission from Ref. [12]

electrochemical sensitivity of the system. In optimized conditions, the developed method demonstrated exceptional sensitivity, with a low LOD 21.10 ng/mL, a broad linear sensing range of 50–500 ng/mL, and a strong specificity for the detection of NGAL in low sample volumes (10 μ L). In real-world use, the developed biosensor was assessed for NGAL detection in human urine, and the findings closely matched those acquired through a conventional ELISA assay. Moreover, in comparison to

the ELISA method, the developed method offers advantages such as reduced analysis time (approximately 30 min per sample), lower sample volume requirements, and decreased operational costs [50]. Zhang et al., developed a nano hybrid utilizing prussian blue (PB) and graphitic- C_3N_4 nanosheets ($g-C_3N_4$) as the signal-generation tags in an enzyme-free electrochemical immunoassay for NGAL [9]. They achieved the deposition of PB nanoparticles with redox capabilities onto $g-C_3N_4$ through an in-situ reduction process. Subsequently, SPCE was modified using NGAL antibodies, and PB- $g-C_3N_4$ nano hybrid served as a signal-generation label for secondary NGAL antibodies (Fig. 8). After introducing the NGAL target and the secondary antibody, a sandwich configuration was established on the surface of the SPCE. By applying a standard potential, typically at 0.13 V (vs. Ag/AgCl), a clearly defined voltametric peak emerged due to the existence of PB on the secondary antibody. In ideal conditions, the peak current displayed a linear increase within the NGAL concentration range from 0.01 to 10 ng/mL, with an LOD of 2.80 pg/mL ($3 \sigma/m$) [9]. The developed method has demonstrated an average precision of less than 12 % in batch-to-batch testing, and there were no interference issues with additional biomarkers associated with other diseases. To validate the precision and consistency of the developed approach, detection of the target NGAL in human serum samples with added NGAL was compared to results obtained through a commercial ELISA, showing good agreement between the two methods [9].

As a two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterial, graphene holds great value in various technological applications. Graphene-derived electrochemical sensors have shown remarkable sensitivity in detecting various biochemical substances. Nevertheless, 2D graphene layers often face stability issues caused by aggregation and re-stacking. A practical approach to addressing this challenge is to create structured 3D graphene networks using 2D graphene components, thereby preserving the inherent stability of graphene properties. Danvirutai et al., reported a highly sensitive and label-free electrochemical sensor for NGAL using a

Fig. 10. (A) Fabrication of AuNPs functionalized Ni-mold substrate, (B) incorporation of anti-NGAL with AuNPs functionalized Ni-mold substrate, and (C) detection of NGAL in cat urine samples. . Reproduced with permission from Ref. [27]

Fig. 11. (A) Preparation of Ag based NGAL biosensor substrate. (B) Mechanism of enzymatic NGAL detection approach. .
Reproduced with permission from Ref. [6]

gold nanoparticle-adorned 3D graphene foam (GF/AuNPs) [12]. The GF/AuNPs substrate offers higher sensitivity towards NGAL detection owing to the following reasons: (i) The large active surface area of 3D GF foam improves the accessibility of AuNPs and provides a larger electrochemical surface area. (ii) The electrical dipoles on 3D GF/Ni foam (Fig. 9A) improve the adsorption of amine functionalities in NGAL. Coupling 11-mercaptopundecanoic acid (11-MUA) with AuNPs facilitated the binding of NGAL antibodies towards the electrochemical assessment of NGAL through the ferri/ferrocyanide redox system [12]. The interfacial dipole layers between GF and Ni formed 3D for further amplifying the redox probe currents and thus significantly enhancing the electrochemical detection sensitivity (Fig. 9B). This method achieved a low LOD of 42.00 pg/mL with an extensive linear range of

0.05–210 ng/mL [12]. To validate specificity, electrochemical tests were conducted to detect NGAL while accounting for potential interference from uric acid and creatinine. The impressive performance achieved can be attributed to the substantial specific surface area of GF and AuNPs, which enhance electron transfer from the analyte through graphene-Ni-Au electric dipole enrichment. The outcomes highlight the potential of the projected platform for achieving non-invasive, ultra-sensitive, highly selective, and electrochemical detection of NGAL [12].

Later on, Wang and co-workers introduced a simple electrochemical immunoassay utilizing a monolayer electrode composed of AuNPs for the detection of NGAL in cat urine samples [27]. To prepare the working electrode, a Ni-mold featuring a concave micro-hemispherical array was first created. This Ni-mold was then employed to imprint the micro-

Fig. 12. (A) Step-by-step NGAL biosensor electrode preparation using anti-NGAL, GaNPs, Re₂O₇, and Si components. .
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Fig. 13. (A) Stepwise construction of BCN nanosheet-based microelectrode inter-junction with peroxidase/thionine/biotinylated anti-NGAL for the detection of NGAL. .

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hemispherical structure on a polyethylene terephthalate (PET) film by the hot embossing method. Subsequently, a thin layer of gold was deposited on an array of micro-hemispherical structures. Following this, AuNPs and 1,6-hexanedithiol were evenly applied to the PET membrane, followed by the immobilization of anti-NGAL, which resulted in the formation of the sensing electrode (Fig. 10A-B). The concentrations of NGAL were assessed through the EIS method, with anti-NGAL bound to the electrode surface. The outcomes indicated that this sensing approach displayed a broad dynamic range of detection from 1 to 100 ng/mL, enabling the differentiation between normal (NGAL concentration < 10 ng/mL) and impaired kidneys. Furthermore, the method exhibited a low limit of detection (0.47 ng/mL) and high sensitivity (10261.8 Ω ng/mL). The applicability of the developed method was verified by analyzing actual urine samples of cats collected from a veterinary hospital, which corroborated the accuracy of this method, showcasing its potential for precise NGAL concentration measurement in cat urine samples (Fig. 10C).

Progress was made on this biosensor, a miniaturized screen-printed electrochemical cell with dual working electrodes, which was developed as the transducer for NGAL detection. In this regard, Neves et al., reported a sensitive miniaturized electrochemical immunosensor substrate for the determination of NGAL (Fig. 11A) [6]. The biosensing method followed a sandwich arrangement, where the specific immune-recognition event was identified with the use of alkaline phosphatase (enzymatic label) and a mixture of 3-indoxyl phosphate and silver (substrate) (Fig. 11B). The analytical output depended on the voltammetric removal of the enzymatically deposited silver. The second working electrode served as a negative control. The outlined method exhibited an LOD of 0.096 ng/mL (3 s/m) in a 50 μ L sample, with the entire assay taking 125 min. The validation of the developed immunosensor was indeed confirmed by testing urine samples with known quantities of the target substance, with a recovery range of 97.40–104.30 % [6]. It is important to mention here that in electrochemical immunosensors, the electrode surface is utilized to immobilize specific antibodies for the purpose of binding with the biomarker [134,140]. Nevertheless, the majority of current electrochemical NGAL biosensors utilize carbon-based materials or polymers, requiring intricate synthesis processes and complex instrumentation.

Therefore, there is an increasing demand for the progress of a simpler method for the fabrication of NGAL biosensors. In a related approach, Das et al., designed a biosensing platform comprised of GaNPs combined with galvanized birhenium heptoxide (Re₂O₇) film on a molecular Si-linker (3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane) for the quantitative detection of NAGL (Fig. 12) [81]. This platform was chosen for its enhanced redox

properties, chemical stability, non-toxicity, controllable dimensions, ease of fabrication, and compatibility with the desired shape [81]. The use of sonication-derived GaNPs galvanized Re₂O₇ film over the Si substrate served as a potential transducer for the detection of NAGL. Under optimized conditions, anti-NGAL antibodies were affixed to the GaNPs/Re₂O₇/Si electrode using a carbodiimide crosslinking agent for the NGAL biosensing assay (Fig. 12). In both differential pulse voltammetry (sensitivity: 0.018 μ A/ng/mL, R² = 0.99) and EIS (detection limit: 2.14 ng/mL), the biosensor demonstrated remarkable performance across a broad sensing range of NGAL concentrations ranging from 25.00 to 650.00 ng/mL and offered excellent selectivity and durability.

The enhanced biosensor performance was mainly attributed to the collective electron transfer involving Re₂O₇ film to GaNPs and GaNPs to electroactive substances. Furthermore, the external 2D gallium oxide shell of GaNPs significantly contributed to improved redox activity, while the metallic core enhanced electrical conductivity. This biosensor exhibited excellent recovery rates when tested with different NGAL concentrations in commercial human serum samples, with a recovery range of 100.24–104.52 %, using the standard addition method, which confirmed its practical applicability. On the other side, Chen et al reported a sensitive electrochemical immunosensing platform for NGAL detection in human serum fluids [49]. This platform utilized an anti-LCN2 antibody-functionalized carbon-fiber microelectrode (CFME) (Fig. 13A). In detail, 2-D boron carbon nitride (BCN) nanosheets offered extensive surface coverage and strong conductivity, which was used for the functionalization of electroactive compound thionine and peroxidase-conjugated anti-LCN2 detection antibodies (Fig. 13B) [49].

The construction of the electrochemical immunosensor involved the covalent attachment of anti-LCN2 capture antibodies to a carbon-fiber microelectrode (CFME), which formed a sandwich-type immunoreaction; the peroxidase within the immunocomplex exhibited favorable electrochemical behavior towards the detection of NGAL, aided by the presence of redox thionine (Fig. 13C) [49]. Under optimal conditions, the BCN-based immunosensing interface showed strong electrochemical responses towards target LCN2 with a dynamic range of 0.001–10 ng/mL and exhibited a LOD of 0.37 pg/mL. Furthermore, the developed immunoassay was applied to detect potential cancer biomarkers in human serum with notable specificity. Clinical serum samples containing target LCN2 were analyzed using the fabricated immunosensor alongside a commercially available human LCN2 ELISA kit as a reference method, yielding closely matching results between the two approaches [49]. In addition to the NGAL biosensing assays mentioned earlier, the pH-meter is a tool that analyzes the hydrogen-ion reactivity in aqueous solutions, demonstrating its acidity or alkalinity expressed as

Fig. 14. (A) Preparation of CLENPs using GA and PASA, followed the functionalization of pAb₂ on the surface of CLENPs. (B) The micro-plate integrated with mAb₁ was used to detect NGAL in the presence of pAb₂-CLENPs via a urea hydrolysis reaction. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [142].

pH. Due to its compact size, affordability, user-friendly operation, and dependable delivery of quantitative outcomes, it ranks among the most commonly utilized electrical devices [141]. Afsahi et al. studied urine pH to understand the correlation between urinary plungers and pH meters in dairy cattle. They compared the pH of urine before and after centrifugation using each technique [141]. Passing-Bablok regression analysis was employed to assess the unity between urinary plungers and pH-meter systems, both before and after the centrifugation. The analysis revealed that there were consistent differences (intercepts) of 0.60 and -1.01 , as well as positive relative differences (slopes) of 0.94 and 1.13, respectively. The overall bias, evaluated using the Bland-Altman plot method, was found to be less than the allowable bias in real urine samples, both before (0.20) and after (0.14) the centrifugation. The regression plot in this study highlighted that urinary plungers can be utilized for assessing urine samples from cattle [141]. On the other side, Qi and co-workers developed a signal transducer tag using urease nanoparticles (CLENPs) for pH meter-based detection of NGAL. For this purpose, the CLENPs were synthesized using glutaraldehyde (GA) and polyaspartic acid (PASA) as major precursors in the desolvation method [142]. The introduction of polyclonal anti-NGAL was achieved on the surface of carboxylated CLENPs in the presence of an amine coupling reagent, which can be used as a signal generation tag (pAb₂-CLENPs) (Fig. 14A). While introducing NGAL antigen, a sandwich-immune complex was formed between the captured NGAL antibody-coated micro-plate (mAb₁/micro-plate) and the pAb₂-CLENPs (Fig. 14B) [142]. The integrated pAb₂-CLENPs on the micro-plate hydrolyzed urea into ammonium (NH_4^+) and carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) ions, which altered the pH of the above reaction mixture, and the observed changes were measured using a hand-held pH meter. It has been proven that the change in pH of the reaction mixture is highly related to the concentration of NGAL targets in the sample, and as a result, the LOD of NGAL was measured up to 5.20 pg/mL. The development of pH meter-based electrochemical biosensing assays was potentially explored for commercial manufacturing of customized lab-on-a-chip devices with hand-held pH meters, ensuring fresh openings for clinical diagnostic tools and biosecurity [142]. The summary of antibody-based functionalized nanostructured detection of NGAL in various real samples is described in Table 2.

5. Conclusion and outlook

In conclusion, the use of electrochemical methods-based biosensing to detect NGAL levels in various real samples holds significant potential for understanding kidney function and its vital role in human health, making it effectively useful for monitoring AKI-related conditions. NGAL serves as a vital marker for kidney injury, and its release is triggered exclusively when the kidneys experience stress due to inflammation and infection. Continuous assessment of its levels in biological fluids may provide valuable information for the early detection of AKI and, in turn, help prevent diabetic nephropathy. Electrochemical biosensor platforms comprised of advanced nanostructured materials have excessive potential for improving the competencies of present molecular diagnostics by permitting fast and precise diagnoses, the incorporation of diagnostic and therapeutic abilities, and the recognition of tailored medicine. Electrochemical NGAL biosensors offer substantial benefits over conventional approaches, including higher sensitivity, faster response time, and the capability to screen NGAL levels in real-time, rendering them a reliable and efficient tool for studying the early stages of the AKI, which is crucial for the design of future POC devices. Still, there are some restrictions on using these bio-recognition elements (antibody, antigen, aptamer, etc.) including lack of stability, expensiveness, and cross-reactivity. In addition, these bio-recognition elements may be prone to denaturation and degradation, which can result in reducing binding affinity and selectivity. However, progress in developing inexpensive, reliable, and potentially sensitive NGAL biosensors faces critical challenges, such as bio-fouling, sensitivity limitations, and stable performance of the recognition interface.

To address the key issues mentioned above, research efforts are continuously advancing in the development of functional nanomaterials integrated into electrochemical biosensing platforms. These platforms display remarkable features for the determination of NGAL in clinical and healthcare applications. Their exclusive electronic, optical, and electrochemical properties, along with their tunable size and structures, make them potential applicants for the analysis of AKI biomarkers in various real samples using various electrochemical techniques. The use of recombinant antibody frameworks, such as single-chain variable (scFv) or antigen-binding fragments (Fab), has the ability to improve the stability of antibodies in comparison to traditional analysis. Research efforts are continuing to focus on enhancing the activity of nanostructured materials, exploring nanotechnology-based biosensing

Table 2
Antibodies functionalized nanostructured biosensing platforms toward the detection of NGAL in various real samples.

Biosensing Platform	Biosensor Construction Steps	Linear Limit	Detection Method	LOD	Real Samples	Ref.
Specific immune-recognition sandwich complex	Steps involved: 4 (i) Capture Ab modified on Dual-SPE WE1 and WE2; (ii) introduction of a blocking agent; (iii) incubation of NGAL (or urine spiked with NGAL) and biotinylated detection Ab; (iv) introduction of streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase conjugate, and finally the detection of NGAL achieved by screening the enzymatic reaction (3-indoxyl phosphate and silver nitrate)	0.1–5 ng/mL	LSV	0.096 µg/mL (3 s/m)	Human urine	[6]
PB and g-C ₃ N ₄ nanosheets	Steps involved: 3 (i) the preparation of PB-g-C ₃ N ₄ nanohybrids with pAb2 secondary antibody; (ii) the mAb1-SPGE was immersed into PSA standard solution; (iii) the resulting SPGE was soaked into pAb2/PB-g-C ₃ N ₄ , and the detection of NGAL was achieved by SWV analysis from –50 mV to 350 mV (vs. Ag/AgCl).	0.001–100 ng/mL	SWV	2.80 pg/mL (3 σ/m)	Human urine and serum	[9]
3-D graphene/nickel foam (GF) decorated with AuNPs	Steps involved: 5 (i) Fabrication of graphene modified nickel foam interface (GF); (ii) electrodeposition of AuNPs on GF interface using constant DC potential of –0.2 V for 30 s (AuNPs/GF); (iii) self-assembly of 11-mercaptopropionic acid on AuNPs/GF interface (MUA/AuNPs/GF); (iv) immobilization of anti-LCN2 on the MUA/AuNPs/GF interface (Anti-LCN2/MUA/AuNPs/GF), and finally the detection of LCN2 (NGAL) was achieved using Fe(CN) ₆ ^{3-/4-} redox probe.	0.05–210 ng/mL	CV	42.00 pg/mL (3.3 SD/s)	Human urine	[12]
Monolayer of AuNPs	Steps involved: 5 (i) The preparation of concave Ni-mold micro-hemispheres; (ii) PET substrates introduced on the as-fabricated nickel mold via the hot embossing process; (iii) introducing Au thin film was the sputtering process, (iv) formation of 1,6-hexanedithiol (HDT) on the Au film via Au-S chemistry; (v) immobilization of anti-NGAL using EDC-NHS chemistry, and the detection of NGAL was achieved using a Fe(CN) ₆ ^{3-/4-} redox probe.	1–100 ng/mL	EIS	0.47 ng/mL (3 σ/m)	Human urine	[27]
GANPs interfaced to annealed dirhenium heptoxide (Re ₂ O ₇) thin-film modified Silicon (Si) substrate	Steps involved: 5 (i) Fabrication of the aminopropyl silane (APS) on the Re ₂ O ₇ thin film, (ii) insertion of GA NPs on the surface of APS/Re ₂ O ₇ thin film, (iii) self-assembly of MUA (SAM) on the GA NPs/APS/Re ₂ O ₇ thin film, (iv) immobilization of anti-NGAL antibodies on the MUA/GA NPs/APS/Re ₂ O ₇ thin film via EDC-NHS chemistry (anti-NGAL/MUA/GA NPs/APS/Re ₂ O ₇ thin film), (v) BSA integration on the anti-NGAL/MUA/GA NPs/APS/Re ₂ O ₇ thin film (BSA/anti-NGAL/MUA/GA NPs/APS/Re ₂ O ₇ thin film) and the detection NGAL achieved using Fe(CN) ₆ ^{3-/4-} redox probe.	25–650 ng/mL	EIS	2.14 ng/mL (3 SD/b)	Human serum	[81]
Electropolymerized aniline and electrospayed graphene/poly-aniline (G/PANI)	Steps involved: 4 (i) Graphene was initially modified on the SPE surface via electrospay method; (ii) the electropolymerization of aniline was carried out from –0.5 V to +1.0 V; (iii) the functionalization of anti-NGAL antibodies using EDC/NHS coupling chemistry by covalent bonding; (iv) BSA integration on the anti-NGAL functionalized G/PANI interface and the detection of NGAL was achieved using PBS solution.	50–500 ng/mL	CV	21.10 ng/mL (3 S _b /m)	Human urine	[50]
Biofunctionalized carbon fiber microelectrode (CFME)	Steps involved: 3 (i) Immobilization of boron carbon nitride (BCN) nanosheets on the surface of CFME; (ii) conjugation of BCN nanosheets with thionine and biotinylated antihuman NGAL antibody was carried out via NHS/EDC-based carbodiimide coupling reaction; (iii) integration of BSA blocking agent, and the detection of NGAL achieved using peroxidase/H ₂ O ₂ reaction.	0.001–10 ng/mL	LSV	0.37 ng/mL (3 S/K)	Human serum	[49]
Signal-transduction tag based on cross-linked urease nanoparticles	Steps involved: 4 (i) Desolvation of urease nanoparticles (CLENPs) in ethanol and GA solution; (ii) functionalization of carboxylated PASA; (iii) immobilization of polyclonal pAb2 NGLA antibodies via EDC and NHS coupling method (pAb2-CLENPs); and (iv) the detection of NGAL was achieved by NGAL capture Abs functionalized microplate in the presence of NGAL and pAb2-CLENPs.	0.01–100 ng/mL	pH meter	5.20 pg/mL (signal-to-noise ratio of 3)	Human serum	[142]

* “s/m”, “σ/m”, “SD/s”, “SD/b”, “S_b/m”, and “S/K” are represented same analysis condition.

Fig. 15. A pictorial display shows the various designs of future wearable electrochemical biosensor platforms for NGAL detection. .
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approaches, and progressing wearable devices. The improved sensitivity of electrochemical biosensors may depend on important factors such as biosensing principles, the design of the biosensing platform, the recognition of transducer elements, the type of biosensing method, and the stability of the biosensing platform. Nevertheless, despite the above factors, the significance of real-time NGAL screening devices offers new insights into clinical practice, and their high utility in healthcare has a substantial impact. Thus, the development of such devices could transform the management of AKI-related illnesses and greatly assist personal healthcare.

Compared to the currently available electrochemical detection methods, the development of flexible or portable electrochemical devices offers the capability to continuously screen biological compounds in real-time by non-invasive means. In particular, progress in non-invasive electrochemical platform-based detection of biomarkers using sweat samples is valuable from a healthcare perspective. It is important to mention that the design of some electronic miniaturization devices shown in Fig. 15 (stretchable/flexible, cloths/paper, microfluidic, surface coatings, and near-field electronic devices) may offer a superior role in integrating newly developed electrochemical biosensing approaches for critical AKI diagnostic purposes. Flexible biosensors combined with lab-on-a-chip systems can comfortably adhere to the human skin surface and validate the usefulness of wearable electrochemical biosensing platforms. Further, the integrated detection of multiple analytes is essential to obtaining disease-related biomarker evidence. The biosensing parameters will certainly endure added developments and modifications in the near future owing to advances in nanomaterial preparation, processing, system integration, and analytical testing techniques. Nevertheless, the chemistry among these elements must be sensibly explored and computed to certify synergistic profits for the healthcare sector.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Bharathi Natarajan: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Palanisamy Kannan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Palaniappan Subramanian:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Govindhan Maduraiveeran:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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